

Reduction of the Perception of Employment Insecurity in the Italian Regions between 2013 and 2019

Istat calculates the value of the "Perception of job insecurity". The value of the "Perception of job insecurity" is defined as the "Percentage of employed people who in the next 6 months believe it is probable to lose their current job and it is little or not at all probable to find another similar one on the total of employed".

The perception of insecurity in the Italian regions in 2019. In 2019, Sardinia ranks first in terms of the perception of job insecurity with an amount of 9.8%, followed by Calabria with an amount of 9.7% and from Basilicata with a value of 9.5%. In the middle of the table there are Friuli-Venezia Giulia and Tuscany with an amount of perception of employment insecurity equal to a value of 5.6%, followed by Molise with an amount equal to 5.5%. Lombardy closes the ranking with an amount equal to 4.5%, Veneto with an amount equal to 3.9% and Trentino-Alto Adige with an amount equal to 3.3%.

Change in the perception of employment insecurity in the period between 2013 and 2019. It is possible to calculate the absolute and percentage change in the perception of employment in the period between 2013 and 2019. Molise is in first place with a value of percentage change in the perception of employment insecurity equal to an amount of -62.59% equal to an absolute value of -9.2. Veneto is in second place for percentage change in the perception of employment insecurity with a value equal to -62.50% or equal to an absolute amount equal to -6.5 units. Piedmont is in third place in the ranking of the percentage change in the period between 2013 and 2019 or equal to a change of -61.67% or equal to an amount of -7.4 units. Liguria closes the ranking with a percentage change value equal to -31.63% equal to -3.1 units, followed by Basilicata with an amount equal to -30.1% equal to -4.1 units, followed by Sardinia with an amount equal to -30.00 units equivalent to -4.2 units.

North. The value of the perception of employment insecurity has improved in Italy in the period between 2013 and 2019 from an amount of 11.10 to an amount of 4.60 units or a variation of -6.50 units equal to a value of -58.56%. In the passage between 2013 and 2014 the value of the perception of job insecurity went from an amount equal to 11.10 units up to a value equal to 8.90 units or a variation equal to an amount of -2.20 units equal to -19.82%. In the passage between 2014 and 2015 the value of the perception of job insecurity decreased from an amount equal to 8.90 units up to a value of 7.30 units or equal to a variation of -1.60 units equal to a variation of -17.98%. In the transition between 2015 and 2016 the value of the perception of job insecurity decreased from an amount equal to 7.30 units up to a value equal to 6.30 units or equal to a variation of -1.00 units equal to a value of -13.705. In the transition between 2016 and 2017 the value of the perception of job insecurity decreased from an amount equal to 6.30 units up to a value equal to 5.40 units or a variation equal to -0.90 equivalent to a variation of -14.29%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018 the value of the perception of job insecurity in the North went from an amount equal to 5.40 units up to a value equal to 5.10 units or a variation equal to an amount of -0.30 units equal to a value of -5.56%. In the passage between 2018 and 2019 the value of the perception of job insecurity went from a value equal to 5.10 units up to a value of 4.60 units or equal to a value of -0.50 units equal to a value of -9.80%.

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Center. The perception of employment insecurity in central Italy decreased from an amount of 12.30 in 2013 to a value of 5.40 in 2019 or a change equal to a value of -6.90 units equal to an amount of 56.10%. In the passage between 2013 and 2014, the perception of the insecurity of employment in the Center decreased from an amount equal to 12.30 to a value of 9.40 or a variation equal to an amount of -2.90 units equal to 23.58%. Below, the value of the perception of employment insecurity for Central Italy decreased from a value of 8.00 in 2015, to a value of 7.10 in 2016, up to a value of 6.70 units in 2017, to reach an amount of 5.60 in 2018 and equal to 5.40 in 2019.

South of Italy. The value of the perception of employment insecurity in the South has decreased from an amount equal to 15.90 units up to a value equal to 8.00 units or a variation equal to an amount of -7.90 units equal to a value of 49.69%. The value of the perception of job insecurity in Southern Italy decreased from an amount equal to 15.90 units up to an amount equal to 13.50 units between 2013 and 2014. Subsequently the value decreased from an amount of 13, 50 units in 2014, up to 11.50 in 2015, 9.70 units in 2016, 8.90 in 2017, 7.90 in 2018 and then growing to 8.00 in 2019.

Clusterization. Clustering is carried out using the k-Means algorithm with t-SNE representation to check if the groupings coincide with the distinction between the various Italian macro-regions. The choice of the number of clusters is optimized using the Silhouette Coefficient. The analysis shows the presence of two clusters, namely:

- Cluster 1: made up of Campania, Sicily, Puglia, Abruzzo, Calabria, Basilicata, Sardinia;
- Cluster 2: made up of Tuscany, Lombardy, Veneto, Piedmont, Valle d'Aosta, Emilia-Romagna, Liguria, Lazio, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Trentino-Alto Adige, Molise, Marche, Umbria.

As is evident, there are essentially two clusters of which the first essentially coincides with Southern Italy while the second corresponds with the Center-North. It follows that the workers of Southern Italy feel the sense of job insecurity with greater intensity than the workers of the Center-North.

Conclusions. The perception of employment insecurity has decreased in all Italian regions. On average in the Italian regions the value of the perception of job insecurity decreased by about 51% in the period between 2013 and 2019. However, in the face of this reduction, which is certainly a positive fact, the difference is still evident between South and Center-North. In fact, the value of the perception of employment insecurity in the South is 73.91% higher than the corresponding value in the North and 48.14% higher than the corresponding value in the Center.

Declarations

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